

INCREASE

Seed diversity catalogue of the Faba Panel

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Compiled by the Plant Genetic Group of SERIDA

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- Version 1-

This graphic document shows the seed diversity included in the Faba Panel (FP). Currently, the document contains. The photos were taken using a Cannon EOS 600D with a 18-135 mm macro zoom lens.

FP032

FP037

FP061

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FP700 – Cornell

FP701 – AB136

FP702 – MUSICA

FP703 – BAT93

FP704 – Sanilac

FP705 – DOR364

FP706 – Planeta

FP707 – IVT214

FP708 – A25

FP709 – B8

FP710 – A2806

FP711 – A4804

FP712 – Xana

FP713 –MDRK

FP714 – G19833

FP715 – Tendergreen

FP716 – La Victorie

FP717 – Garrafal Oro

FP718 – TU

FP719 – Midas

FP720 – Granjina